

THE SPIRIT OF A NEW ERA: THE IDEOSPHERE GUIDING UZBEKISTAN TOWARDS DEMOCRACY

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Annotation: This article covers the theoretical-philosophical aspects of studying the relationship between the development of a democratic society and the renewal of the society's ideosphere. It also analyzes the influence of the development of a democratic society on the renewal of the ideosphere and its interdependence.

Keywords: ideosphere, spirituality, enlightenment, education, culture, society, development, globalization, democracy, ideology, identity.

In the process of renewal of the societal ideosphere, the civil society has provided each individual with broad opportunities to ensure the rights to independent thinking, freedom of speech, belief, and creativity. As a result of this, the establishment of cultural institutions, creative associations, non-state educational institutions, physical education and sports clubs, federations in the spiritual and cultural sphere became one of the important reforms in the ideosphere of society [1]. It is evident that the democratic changes being implemented in our country, in turn, create a process of spiritual and educational renewal in its ideosphere. Additionally, it develops through the customs and values that form the basis of the ideosphere of the society, serving to guide future generations in their upbringing.

The tasks set by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the modernization of the state and society require realistic thinking and comprehensive study of the system of value criteria and ideas about the values that take priority in the society's ideosphere. It also demands a comprehensive study of the values of citizens, especially young people. This allows not only to determine the spiritual relations of the development of the society's ideosphere in the country, but also to clarify whether it is moving in the direction of socio-cultural modernization or transformation of traditional values for Uzbekistan [2].

Spirituality, enlightenment, political consciousness and culture of citizens are of urgent importance in understanding democratic values in the ideosphere of society. Based on this, the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, paid special attention to the following in his Address to the Oliy Majlis: "As the sages of the

East have said, “The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good education, and the greatest poverty is ignorance”! Therefore, for all of us, acquiring modern knowledge, becoming the owner of true enlightenment and high culture should become a continuous vital need. In order to achieve this development, we need to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This gives us the opportunity to take the shortest path to ascension. After all, information technologies are deeply penetrating all areas of the world today” [3].

Indeed, until we achieve democratic development and until our measures and strategic reforms are aligned with the scope of their benefits, the substance and extent of spiritual progress will not reach a high level. This is related to a significant development in the society’s ideosphere, including fundamentally changing citizens’ consciousness and thinking, eliminating the apathy inherited from the autocratic regime, and, based on this, uniting towards national revival and progress through our national strategic reforms and actively participating in these processes. Only a society with high moral and intellectual wealth can truly value democratic principles, while, conversely, uneducated and ignorant people, by supporting totalitarian regimes and conservative ideologies, prove to be obstacles to democratic development, as life itself demonstrates. For this purpose, in the current globalization process, it is necessary to create conditions for all layers of society to enjoy these values, combining the best examples of national and world culture, and to develop a strategy to pass them on to the next generation. In this regard, supporting the renewal of music, theater, cinema, sculpture, painting and many other art fields in our country, introducing these national art forms to the world has become one of the priority directions of our state policy.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev paid special attention about this in a briefing on the results of the consultative meeting of the leaders of the Central Asian countries: “Central Asia is one of the few regions in the world where blood-related peoples have been living peacefully and harmoniously for centuries. We are closely connected by common history and culture, one holy religion, similar mentality, spiritual and moral values and traditions, and inseparable friendship” [4].

The development of our country depends, first of all, on its identity, its spiritual potential in the ideosphere of society, and the rise of its national consciousness. Therefore, striving for economic well-being should not prevent the spiritual and intellectual growth of the people. Spiritual maturity and

educational excellence in the ideosphere of the society has been a unique aspect of the Uzbek people during the long history. Harmonizing our people's traditional values with the values of the current democratic society is a guarantee for our country to further develop in the near future and secure a worthy place in the global community.

In conclusion, analyzing the interconnection between democracy, the development of a democratic society, and spiritual renewal in the ideosphere of society, as well as the philosophical essence of related concepts, holds significant scientific and theoretical importance. Due to independence, Uzbekistan chose to follow the path of democratic development. For this, it was necessary to renew the ideosphere of the society from a spiritual and educational point of view. In doing so, the ideological and ideological goals and principles of the development of society related to the former Soviet system were abandoned. In the development of the society, relying on the foundations of the national idea, the society was put on a new ideological foundation. As a result, the development of a democratic society began to be implemented through ideological renewal. Based on this, it can be said that many reforms necessary for national-spiritual revival and realization of national identity in the ideosphere of society were implemented.

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